

Sources of dual resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) and green leafhopper (GLH)

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We evaluated 100 rice accessions from the 1985 International Rice Whitebacked Planthopper Nursery for resistance to WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* under greenhouse conditions; 15 accessions were identified as resistant. The WBPH-resistant varieties were further evaluated for resistance to GLH *Nephotettix virescens*, using the standard seedbox screening test.

Pregerminated seeds were sown in 60- × 40- × 10-cm seedboxes. Ptb 33 was the resistant check and TN1 the susceptible check. Each accession was replicated five times for each insect species. Seedlings were infested with 8 2d-instar nymphs of WBPH and 5 2d-instar nymphs of GLH/seedling 7 d after sowing. Damage was rated using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* when 90-100% of TN1 plants had died.

All 15 accessions were resistant to WBPH and to GLH (see table). □

Resistance of selected rice accessions to WBPH and GLH. Greenhouse, TNAU, Coimbatore, India, 1985.

Rice accession	Damage rating ^a	
	WBPH	GLH
Chempan	1 a	1 a
Chempan pandi	3 b	1 a
Horonamawee	1 a	1 a
IR9852-22-3	1 a	1 a
IR13427-40-2-3-3	1 a	1 a
IR13429-196-1	1 a	1 a
IR13475-7-3-2	1 a	1 a
IR15429-268-1-2-1	3 b	1 a
IR15527-21-2-3	3 b	1 a
IR15529-256-1	3 b	1 a
IR15795-151-2-3-2-2	1 a	1 a
IR28154-101-3-2	1 a	1 a
Podiwi A8	3 b	1 a
Valsara Champara	1 a	1 a
Sufaida 172	1 a	1 a
Ptb 33 (resistant check)	1 a	1 a
TN1 (susceptible check)	9 c	9 b

^aMean of 5 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

Yield of gall midge (GM)-resistant rice varieties after early pulse crop at Hyderabad

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Yields of GM-resistant rices WGL 20506, WGL 23022, and WGL 16145 and cultivar Surekha following a green manure crop were examined. An early pulse crop was harvested in early Aug. The trial compared broadcasting sprouted seed and transplanting 30-d-old seedlings. Sowing was on 1 Aug and 16 Aug. Seed rate for broadcasting was 120 kg/ha, spacing for transplanting was 10 × 10 cm. Recommended fertilizer was 80-22 kg NP/ha. N was applied in three splits, all the P was applied basally.

Yield of promising GM-resistant rices following a green manure crop on 2 planting dates, Hyderabad, India.^a

Cultivar	Yield (t/ha)			
	2 Aug planting		16 Aug planting	
	BC	TP	BC	TP
WGL 20506	3.5	3.5	3.6	3.3
WGL 23022	3.6	4.0	3.3	3.9
WGL 16145	3.3	5.0	2.4	4.4
Surekha	3.5	5.0	2.7	4.4
Mean yield	3.6	4.4	3.0	4.0

^aBC = broadcast, TP = transplanted.

Transplanted crops yielded higher than broadcast crops (see table). Increases were 34.7% in WGL 16145 and 30.2% in Surekha in the first planting and 16.5% in WGL 23022, 40.5% in WGL 16145, and 38.8% in Surekha in the second planting. □

Resistance of selected *Oryza sativa* and *O. brachyantha* cultivars to the rice leaffolder (LF)

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Mass screening in the IRRI greenhouse has yielded cultivars with resistance or moderate resistance to the LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée. Oviposition, larval survival, and host preference were studied on three

resistant wild rices and five resistant cultivars.

One-month-old seedlings were planted in 5-cm-diam clay pots at 5 plants/pot per cultivar in a randomized complete block design with 5 replications. For the oviposition treatment, each replication was enclosed in a fiberglass net and 50 pairs of newly emerged adults were introduced. Eggs laid were counted after 3 d.

For larval survival measurement,

Table 1. Larval survival and oviposition preference of rice LF on *Oryza brachyantha* and *O. sativa* cultivars.^a IRRI, 1986.

<i>Oryza</i> spp.	Accession no.	Larval survival (%)	Oviposition preference
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101232	2 a	71 a
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101233	14 a	63 a
<i>O. brachyantha</i>	101234	10 a	80 a
<i>O. sativa</i>			
Darukasail	45493	56 bc	128 b
Kamalbhog	49020	52 bc	176 c
Choorapundy	48529	38 b	131 b
TKM6	237	44 bc	172 c
TN1	105	64 c	227 d

^aAv of 5 replications. n = 10. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT.